

INDIA'S GROWTH PERSPECTIVE- AN ACADEMIC BREAK ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: By applying the formal applied Structural Break Methodologies, often we get abreak point or multiple break points without much economic significance. The break points often are termed as outliers and wiping them out, we get the same trend as before in the trend trajectory. Therefore, the following academic breaks are imposed by the author observing the economic significance. Although the breaks are based upon a postulate analysis, but the significance of them are undeniable. Level Effects (based on Postulate Analysis) on a Non-Stationary Time Series determines the Break Dates. The Postulate Analysis is based on 'Dooming Insignificant Breaks' and averaging the 'pre-level effect' growth rates prior to the Level Effect Growth Date and averaging the 'post-level effect' growth rates after the Level Effect Growth Date. No movement towards the 'Stationarity' of the time series is required. No requirement of Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test is required to determine the break dates. No requirement of 'min RSS' or 'max F' to determine the break dates. These are simply methods to determine the 'Outlier' dates and not the break dates in general. The Zivott-Andrews break, Amit Sen break and the Bai-Perron break, all these breaks determined only outliers. My break determination through the "Level Effects of the Trends" actually determines the breaks.

Keywords: Academic Structural Break as against Zivott-Andrews Structural Break, Amit Sen Structural Break, Bai-Perron Structural Change. Input Output Method, Manufacturing led Growth engine by Services Revolution

JEL Classification: C22, C67, O14, O50.

INTRODUCTION: By applying the formal applied Structural Break Methodologies, often we get a break point or multiple break points without much economic significance. The break points often are termed as outliers and wiping them out, we get the same trend as before in the trend trajectory. Therefore, the following academic breaks are imposed by the author observing the economic significance. Although the breaks are based upon a postulate analysis, but the significance of them are undeniable. Level Effects (based on Postulate Analysis) on a Non-Stationary Time Series determines the Break Dates. The Postulate Analysis is based on 'Dooming Insignificant Breaks' and averaging the 'pre-level effect' growth rates prior to the Level Effect Growth Date and averaging the 'post-level effect' growth rates after the Level Effect Growth Date. No movement towards the 'Stationarity' of the time series is required. No requirement of Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test is required to determine the break dates. No requirement of 'min RSS' or 'max F' to determine the break dates. These are simply methods to determine the 'Outlier' dates and not the break dates in general.

If we observe the Indian economy from 1900 to 2020, then there exists several Structural Breaks in the Indian Economy that leads to the Growth and Development as well as Stagnation of the Indian economy through the structural change. If we observe the Indian Economy from 1900 to 2020 then Trend in GDP Growth rate would look like the following Figure-I.

The growth rate of GDP in 1900 to 1945 period was 0% and from 1945 to 1965 it was 6% (source Wikipedia). Terminal Growth Rate at each stage is to be taken because the growth rates are projected approximately and it is an analysis based on postulate based on reason. So, the First Structural Break (S.B. I) in the growth rate of Indian GDP is in 1945 (Figure I).

REASON: Reason behind this is prior to 1945 India, under colonial legacy, severely exploited by the colonial rule of British Government, and thus failed to grow both in terms of Agriculture and Industry (Bipan Chandra, "The colonial legacy", 'The Indian Economy, Problems and Perspective' Edited by BimalJalan, Penguin Books, 1993). The growth in both agriculture and industry was nothing but zero (0) if not negative. Severe exploitation by British without enhancing the irrigational infrastructure of the land made it infertile or sterile. Extraction of raw materials from India at almost zero (0) cost and export finished articles in

India at highest revenue or price destroyed India's industrial structure or sectoral structure. So during 1900 to 1945 colonial India experienced zero growth rate in overall aspect.

However, at 1947, India got independence and their after, in the First Plan and in the Second Plan, optimum importance was given to both agriculture and industry so that on an average the growth rate of India became 6% which was quite comprehensive corresponding to the then Industrial nation's growth structure and modest by the standard of the then other developing countries (Kuznets, (1971), Chenery and Taylor (1968)).

FIGURE 1: GROWTH TRAJECTORY OF THE INDIAN ECONOMY CORRESPONDING TO THE SEVEN SIGNIFICANT STRUCTURAL BREAKS ON 1945, 1964, 1965, 1979, 2007, 2020 and 2021 BASED ON ECONOMIC ANALYSIS.

The First Five Year Plan (1951-1956) aimed at solving the food crisis in India and ease the critical raw material situation, particularly the acute shortage of raw cotton and raw jute. Accordingly, the First Plan gave the highest priority to Agriculture, specifically food production, by allotting 31% of the total plan outlay on agriculture. The production target in **food grains** during the First Plan was exceeded, for instance, against the target of about 62 million tonnes, actual production of food grains came to nearly 67 million tonnes. For **oil seeds**, target was 5.5 million tonnes. Actual achieved was 5.6 million tonnes. For **sugarcane** target was 63 million tonnes. Actual was 60 million tonnes. For **cotton**, target was 4.2 million tonnes. Actual was 5.4 million tonnes. For jute target was 5.4 million tonnes. Actual was 4.2 million tonnes.

The Second Plan and the Third Plan followed the same pattern in Agriculture, although the Third Plan performed somewhat less in the last year (1964-65) due to severe drought in the country for consecutive 5 years from 1964 to 1968.

Since 1950 -51, since the first plan, considerable importance was attached to the provision of canal irrigation. The first plan devoted as much as 25% of total plan outlay on irrigation and created 3 million hectares of irrigation potential. Irrigational investment in the first five year plan in India was about 4.41 billion and created Bhakra, Hirakud and Damodar valley dams. India's investment in irrigation has increased over years. *In 1945, only 10% of total agricultural land was reliably irrigated and in 1965 only 15% total agricultural land was reliably irrigated (self-calculation based on 35% = 90mha in 1995 and in each 5 year from 1950 – 1995, increase in irrigation area from 22.6mha in 1950 to 90mha at 1995).*

Corresponding to the Industrial sector in the First Five Year Plan, the foundation for industrialisation was laid although spurt in industrialization through the heavy industries came from the Second Plan (1956 -1960) through the Industrial Policy Resolution, 1956. The actual investment in public sector on organised industry was Rs 870 Crores. Private sector investment was Rs 675 Crores during the Second Plan period. Although we know that the private investors were not capable to take risk of investment in the industrial sector of a poverty-stricken and destructured, destroyed, dismantled Indian economy under colonial legacy, the Government of India in post-independence period had to come forward to become the spearhead to industrialize the economy/nation and bear the risk associated with it (risk of bottlenecks and non-profitability). Once the situation seemed favourable, then only the private

investors came forward to bear the risk of industrialisation so that the country can become developed.

Total investment in industries during the second plan was Rs 1810 Crores i.e. 30% of the total investment was on Industry during the Second Plan.

The industrial pattern sought to be developed during the second plan was conceived in terms of the following priorities-

(i) Increased production of Iron and Steel and of heavy engineering and machine building industries.

(ii) Expansion of capacity in respect of other development commodities and producer goods such as Aluminium, Cement, Chemical Pulp, Dyestuffs and Phosphatic Fertilisers and of Essential Drugs.

(iii) Modernisation and Re-Equipment of important national industries which have already come into existence such as Jute and Cotton Textiles and Sugar.

(iv) Fuller utilisation of existing installed capacity in industries where there are gaps between capacity and production; and

(v) Expansion of capacity of consumer goods keeping in view the requirements of common production programmes and the production targets for the decentralised sector of the industry.

During Second Plan, Rourkella Steel plant in Orissa, Bhilai Steel plant in Madhya Pradesh and Durgapur Steel plant in West Bengal was formed. Most of the investments in Second Plan were in heavy and basic industries. There was also rapid expansion of machine building industries, for use in Agriculture and Transport.

In the sphere of village and small industries, substantial progress was recorded. About 60 industrial estates comprising 1000 small factories were set up which was commendable by the then standards.

In the Third Plan, total investment in industries was Rs 3000 Crores (almost double than the Second Plan) out of which, public sector drew about Rs 1700 Crores and private sector drew Rs 1300 Crores. Except for the year 1964- 65, industrial output increased steadily at the rate of 7.6% per annum. The average growth rate of the industries during 1945 to 1965 was thus at most 6%.

The second structural break (SB II) in the Indian economy comes in 1964 with Industrial Deceleration. The third structural break is at 1965 (SBIII) (Figure I).

REASON:The last period of the Third Plan performed somewhat less so that the system of five year plans were withdrawn by the Planning Commission of India and Three(3) Annual Plans were implemented from 1966 - 1969 which were called 'Plan Holiday'. However these plans (Annual Plans) were unable to pull the economy from fallout and hence they were abandoned too. This led to **Industrial Deceleration**.

Industrial Deceleration:*Due to the draught in the country during 1964 to 1968, due to the first oil price hike in 1973 and due to the second oil price hike in 1979, the India's economy experienced a fallout and stagnation in the industrial sector so that the growth rate toppled from modest 6% to the **Hindu rate of growth** of mere 3% during 1965 to 1979 (almost close to the growth rate of 0% during 1900 to 1945) (**ineffective growth implies 0%=3% in terms of capacity utilisation**).*

Definition of industrial sickness (1985)SICA: "Sick industrial company" means an industrial company which has:

- (i) Accumulated losses in any financial year which are equal to 50% or more of its average net worth during four(4) years immediately preceding such financial year; or
- (ii) failed to repay its debt within any three consecutive quarters on demand made in writing for its repayment by a creditor or creditors of such company.

Reason of industrial Declaration/sickness during 1965 to 1979(Terms of Trade Analysis by Tamarajakshi(1969 and 1977); Mitra(1977))

According to Tamarajakshi (1969&1977), Intersectoral barter Terms of Trade(TOT) exists between the Agricultural sector and Non-Agricultural sector. Tamarajakshi has shown that from 1965 onwards for a decade, there was a sharp movement in Terms of Trade against non- agricultural sector (Manufacturing). This analysis of Tamarajakshi signified a relative stagnation in Industrial sector but without much analysis. Mitra (1977), posing the problem in a Kaleckian perspective, analysed the "Industrial Deceleration" of mid-sixties to a relative fall in the demand for manufacturers (probably due to fall in agricultural demand for finished manufactured goods due to draught and oil price hike) consequent upon the shift in the terms of trade against manufacturing and in

favour of agriculture due to excess supply of manufacturing and lack of demand for manufacturing. The manufacturing sector was hit severely probably because the operative sunk cost of the Manufacturing sector is much much higher than the Agriculture sector (for example, Petro Refining Sector and Petroleum Sector). This had led to severe loss making in the Manufacturing sector leading to Industrial Deceleration. Side by side, the TOT favoured the Agriculture sector due to existence of strong Feudal Class lobby in India, which did not allowed the fall in the agricultural goods prices thereby leading to Class Struggle between the agriculture sector and industrial sector (Mitra 1977).

In a different opinion, the first oil price hike and the second oil price hike created adverse supply shock thereby creating cost push inflation and thus creating lack of demand for manufactured goods and industrial sickness/ deceleration 1965-1979 (Sinha 2015).

The fourth structural break (SB.IV) in the Indian economy comes at 1979.

Prior to 1979, during the period 1965-1979, the growth rate was averaged at 3%. Ineffective Hindu Rate of Growth in terms of capacity utilisation: Increasing Returns to Scale versus Increasing Cost because prior to a particular level of growth, cost of production is increasing whereas after that level of growth and higher growth, cost of production becomes decreasing due to Increasing Returns to Scale.

Increasing returns to scale operates only through Block Pricing. So production costs become decreasing, higher and higher the size of the block becomes, after obtaining the block, leading to excess supply of the commodity relative to its demand. Whereas, lower and lower the size of the block, it is becoming difficult to operate production because inputs are available only in blocks and fragmented blocks are very costly to be utilised, leading to excess demand of the commodity relative to its supply. Smaller and smaller are the fragments, more and more difficult to utilise them in production- so more and more costlier;(example-Petro Refining Sector and Petroleum Sector).

But post 1979 experienced a spurt in the Industrial Manufacturing Sector Engined by the Service Sector Revolution leading to 10% growth which is Double digit growth in 2007.

But, again 2007 is the fifth structural break point (S.B.V) because post 2007 growth toppled.

After 2008 due to Global Financial Crisis Recession, growth rate toppled to reach **Hindu Rate of Growth of 4% in 2019.** In 2020, due to Covid Pandemic, growth rate reached to a massive low of (- 7%). But in 2021, we recovered to double digit growth again (10% growth rate).

So, our sixth structural break (SB VI) point exists in 2020.

Based on stunning performance of the manufacturing and services sector, economy again reached to the boom of 10% level of growth in 2021. **2021 is our seventh structural break (SB VII) and growth remains at 10%.**

This above Growth Trajectory of FIGURE-I shows that 'Permanent Growth' has never been achieved by the Indian economy.

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